

Preparation and Characterization of *Bis*-Dithiocarbamato Complexes of *Bis*-Biphenyl Tin(IV)

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Bis-dithiocarbamato complexes of *bis*-*p*-biphenyl tin(IV) of the type $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2 - Sn(S_2CNR'R')_2$, (where R=Me, Et or *i*-pr; R' = $-CH_2C_6H_5$; NRR' = piperidine, 4-methylpiperidine, morpholine, 2:6 dimethylmorpholine or N-methylpiperazine), have been prepared by the reaction of appropriate anhydrous sodium salt of dithiocarbamic acid with $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2SnCl_2$ in acetone. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, i.r. and 1H n.m.r. spectroscopy. Molecular weight determination in C_6H_6 and conductivity measurement in $PhNO_2$ indicated these complexes to be monomeric and non-electrolytic. On the basis of i.r. spectra bidentate mode of bonding between tin and dithiocarbamate ligand has been suggested.

SINCE the first report on phenyl tin dithiocarbamates¹ in 1965, a considerable number of dithiocarbamato complexes of alkyl or aryl tin(IV) have been prepared by various methods^{1,2,3}. The bidentate behaviour of dithiocarbamate ligand in $R_2Sn(IV)$ and $RSn(IV)N,N$ -disubstituted dithiocarbamato complexes is well established^{1,4-7}. Complexes of the type $R_2Sn(R'_2DTC)_2$ (where R=alkyl or halogen) show i.r. spectra and dipole moment consistent with a *cis* arrangement of the R groups. The Mössbauer of a number of complexes were examined and on the basis of quadruple splitting (1.7 mm sec^{-1}), a *cis*-octahedral structure was postulated for bi-phenyl tin(IV) *bis*-dithiocarbamates. On the basis of larger splittings a lower coordination number for the tin atom was suggested for the analogous dialkyl complexes. The structure of the $R_2SnS_2CNR'_2$ complexes is rather uncertain, since no conclusive evidence has been advanced for either a penta or tetra coordinated tin atom in these species³. However, in a recent communication an unsymmetric (an isobidentate) bonding of dithiocarbamate moiety has been suggested in some $Ph_2SnS_2CNR_2$ complexes⁹ on the basis of 1H n.m.r. studies.

The present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of some new *bis*-*p*-biphenyl tin(IV) *bis*-dithiocarbamato complexes of the type $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2Sn(S_2CNR'R')_2$ where (R=Me, Et or *i*-pr and R' = $-CH_2C_6H_5$; or NRR' = piperidine, 4-methylpiperidine, morpholine, 2:6 dimethyl morpholine or N-methylpiperazine). Their i.r. and 1H n.m.r. studies suggest the bidentate mode of bonding between tin and dithiocarbamato group.

Experimental

Reagents and Techniques :

Well dried and purified solvents such as C_6H_6 , CH_2Cl_2 , acetone, petroleum ether were used. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality. For conductivity measurements $PhNO_2$ was purified as described by Fay and Lowry¹⁰.

$(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2SnCl_2$ was prepared by the reaction of $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_4Sn$ and $SnCl_4$ in 1:1 molar ratio in a sealed tube^{11,12}. $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_4Sn$ was prepared from *p*- $BrC_6H_4 - C_6H_5$, $SnCl_4$ and Na in benzene by Wurtz reaction. $SnCl_4$ used was prepared by the action of pure and dry Cl_2 gas on tin metal.

The sodium salts of N-substituted dithiocarbamic acid¹³ were prepared by the reaction of appropriate amine, CS_2 and NaOH in aqueous medium at 10° . These sodium salts were dried *in vacuo* first at room temperature and then at 110° , till rendered anhydrous (i.r. spectrum).

A. Preparation of $(p-C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2 - Sn(S_2CNMeBz)_2$:

(0.4957 g, 1 m mol) $(C_6H_5 - C_6H_4)_2SnCl_2$ and (0.438 g, 2 m mol) $NaS_2CNMeBz$ were refluxed in acetone (50 cm^3) for 30 min. NaCl formed during the reaction was filtered off after cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature. The filtrate was concentrated to 10 cm^3 *in vacuo* and petroleum ether (60-80) was added dropwise with constant

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA FOR *Bis*(BIPHENYL)-TIN-*Bis*-DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES

Complex	Conductivity ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Molarity × 10 ⁻⁵	Found (Calcd)%				M.W. Found (Calcd)	M.P.	Colour
			C	H	N	Sn			
1. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ CNMeBz) ₂	0.29	5	62.2 (61.7)	4.9 (4.65)	3.12 (3.43)	13.9 (14.68)	831 (817)	105°	Faint yellow
2. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ CNEtBz) ₂	0.30	5	62.9 (62.48)	5.4 (4.97)	2.8 (3.31)	13.4 (14.20)	856 (845)	108°	Faint yellow
3. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ CNi-PrBz) ₂	0.28	4	64.1 (63.3)	5.9 (5.34)	3.8 (3.21)	13.15 (13.63)	878 (873)	115°	Faint yellow
4. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ C Pipd) ₂	0.31	5	56.8 (56.64)	5.5 (5.10)	3.12 (3.76)	16.8 (15.97)	852 (745)	100°	Yellowish white
5. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ C 4-Me Pipd) ₂	0.32	6	59.68 (59.12)	5.1 (5.43)	3.32 (3.62)	15.1 (15.39)	885 (773)	105°	Yellowish white
6. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ C Me Pipz) ₂	0.25	3	56.9 (55.74)	5.8 (5.16)	6.6 (7.24)	15.96 (15.48)	761 (775)	210°	White
7. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ C Mor) ₂	0.28	5	53.7 (53.14)	4.08 (4.54)	3.21 (3.74)	15.2 (15.89)	760 (749)	110°	Whitish
8. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn-(S ₂ C 2,6 diMe Mor) ₂	0.28	4	56.03 (56.64)	5.67 (5.22)	2.6 (3.48)	13.9 (14.78)	793 (805)	115°	Whitish

shaking to ensure the complete precipitation. A yellowish white precipitate was collected on a G4 sintered glass frit and dried *in vacuo*. The residue on recrystallization from a 1 : 1 mixture of CH₂Cl₂ and petroleum ether (40-60°) gave a faint yellow crystalline product in >90% yield. Analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

The other dithiocarbamato complexes were prepared in high yield by the same procedure as given above.

Physical Measurements :

The i.r. spectra in the region 4000-250 cm⁻¹ were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model-621 grating spectrometer using KBr pellets. ¹H n.m.r. spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer at a sweep width of 900 Hz using TMS as internal standard. The molecular weight of the complexes were determined ebulliscopically in benzene and conductivity measurements were carried out in PhNO₂ using Beckman R-18 conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported herein have been prepared by the reaction of sodium salt of the respective dithiocarbamic acid on (*p*-C₆H₅-C₆H₄)₂SnCl₂ in acetone.

(where R = Me, Et or *i*-pr and R' = CH₂C₆H₅; or NRR' = piperidine, 4-methylpiperidine, morpholine, 2 : 6 dimethyl morpholine or N-methylpiperazine).

The isolated products were of good purity indicated by satisfactory results of elemental analyses (Table 1), ¹H n.m.r. spectroscopy (Table 3)

TABLE 2—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES OBSERVED IN THE I.R. SPECTRA OF *Bis-p*-BIPHENYL TIN(IV) DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES

Complexes	Position of band (in cm ⁻¹)		
	ν(C-N)	ν(C-S)	ν(M-S)
1. C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ CNMeBz) ₂	1495s	1010s	385m
2. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ CNEtBz) ₂	1505s	1000s	390m
3. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ CN <i>i</i> -PrBz) ₂	1495s	1005s	370m
4. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ C Pipd) ₂	1509s	998s	378m
5. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ C 4-Me Pipd) ₂	1485s	1000s	370m
6. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ C Me Pipz) ₂	1485s	1005s	380m
7. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ C Mor) ₂	1490s	995s	390m
8. (C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Sn(S ₂ C 2,6 diMe Mor) ₂	1468s	1000s	365m

and sharp melting points. These complexes are crystalline white to faint yellow in colour and are considerably stable in inert dry atmosphere, but hydrolyse very slowly in moist air. These complexes are soluble in CHCl₃, CCl₄, CH₂Cl₂, C₆H₆ and are insoluble in petroleum ether.

I.r. Spectra :

The interpretation of i.r. spectra of dithiocarbamates of transition and non-transition metals had aroused considerable interest both diagnostically as well as to assess the nature of bonding of the dithiocarbamate ligand^{2,14-17}. In the i.r. spectra of these complexes, three main regions are important (i) the region 1550-1450 cm⁻¹ which is associated with the thioureide band due to ν(C-N) vibration of S₂C=NRR' ligand, (ii) the region

TABLE 3—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFTS (τ VALUES IN p.p.m.) IN CDCl_3 FOR DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{IV})$

Complexes	Resonance due to biphenyl protons			Resonance due to proton of groups attached to N-atom of DTC ligand	
	d	t	d		
1. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNMeBz})_2$	2.08	2.20	2.50	4.83 (due to $-\text{CH}_2$ of $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$)	6.64 (due to $-\text{CH}_3$)
2. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEtBz})_2$	2.39	2.60	2.72	4.95 (due to $-\text{CH}_2$ of $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$)	6.22 ($-\text{CH}_2$) 8.77 ($-\text{CH}_3$)
3. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CNi-PrBz})_2$	2.16	2.40	2.62	4.80 (due to $-\text{CH}_2$ of $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$)	6.5 ($\rightarrow\text{CH}$) 8.85 ($-\text{CH}_3$)
4. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{C Pipd})_2$	1.94	2.36	2.60	6.08 ($-\text{NCH}_3$)	8.36 ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$)
5. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{C 4-Me Pipd})_2$	1.98	2.41	2.64	5.3 ($-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$)	6.92 ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$) 8.5 ($-\text{CH}$) 9.1 ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$)
6. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{CMe Pipz})_2$	1.99	2.35	2.58	5.88 ($-\text{NCH}_3$)	7.5 ($-\text{NCH}_3$) 7.68 ($-\text{CH}_3$)
7. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{C Mor})_2$	1.94	2.36	2.6	6.13 ($-\text{NCH}_3$)	7.85 ($-\text{OCH}_2$)
8. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{S}_2\text{C 2,6 diMe-Mor})_2$	1.95	2.39	2.63	5.37, 7.27 ($-\text{NCH}_3$)	6.3 ($-\text{CH}$) 8.83 ($-\text{CH}_3$)

1050-950 cm^{-1} which is associated with $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{S})}$ vibration and (iii) the region 400-350 cm^{-1} , associated with $\nu_{(\text{M}-\text{S})}$ vibration.

The presence of an absorption band around 1500 cm^{-1} is accepted as arising from a polar structure as shown below :

The increasing donor character in R or R' provides the stability to this structure and increases $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{N})}$ ^{17,18}. Only one band appearing in the region 1050-950 cm^{-1} was assumed by Ugo and Bonati² as characteristic of symmetrically bonded bidentate ligand, however, two bands indicate one uncomplexed ($\text{C}=\text{S}$) and one complexed ($\text{C}-\text{S}$) group, therefore appearance of two bands $\sim 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the monodentate mode of binding. Brinkhoff and Gotens¹⁹ and Colapietro *et al.*²⁰ have indicated that for the ligand bonded slightly unsymmetrically, two bands with the separation $< 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears at $\sim 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band appearing at $\sim 380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is characteristics for $\nu_{(\text{M}-\text{S})}$ in these complexes.

In the i.r. spectra of the complexes described in this paper (Table 2), a band appears at $\sim 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is characteristic of $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{N})}$ of $\text{S}_2\text{C}=\text{NRR}'$ whereas another band appears at $\sim 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is characteristic of $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{S})}$. Only one band is observed in the region $\sim 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that in these complexes dithiocarbamate ligands are bidentate and symmetrically bonded to tin metal. Sharp band $\sim 380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to Sn-S bond in these complexes.

¹H n.m.r. Spectra :

The benzyl group in *bis-p*-biphenyl tin(IV) *bis*-dithiocarbamate complexes (No. 1-3, Table 3) is

indicated by the presence of a singlet $\sim 4.8 \tau$ due to $-\text{CH}_2$ protons however signal due to phenyl protons of benzyl group get mixed with the proton signals due to biphenyl ligand. Complex No. 1 shows a sharp singlet at 6.64 τ due to N- CH_3 protons. Complex No. 2 shows a quaternion at 6.22 τ (CH_2 protons) and a triplet at 8.77 τ (due to $-\text{CH}_3$ protons) of the ethyl group. In complex No. 3, a multiplet at 6.5 τ and a doublet at 8.85 τ due to the $\rightarrow\text{CH}$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ protons identify the i-pr group.

The piperidine group in compound no. 4 is identified with the appearance of two sharp signals $\sim 6.08 \tau$ (due to $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ protons) and $\sim 8.36 \tau$ (due to $\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$ protons)²¹⁻²³. A doublet at 5.3 τ ($\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), a triplet at 6.92 τ ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$), a multiplet at 8.5 τ ($-\text{CH}$) and a doublet at 9.1 τ ($\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$) protons characterize the presence of 4-methylpiperidine group in complex No. 5. The N-methylpiperazine group in complex No. 6 shows two types of resonance signals due to N- CH_2 protons, i.e. a triplet at 5.88 τ due to CH_2 protons bounded to the N of the DTC group and a triplet at 7.5 τ due to CH_2 protons on the other N bonded to the CH_3 group. The CH_3 protons show a singlet at 7.68 τ ²⁴. The morpholine group in complex No. 7 is indicated with the presence of two types of resonance signals due to CH_2 protons, i.e. at 6.13 τ ($-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ protons) and 7.85 τ ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ protons)²⁴. The 2,6 dimethyl morpholine group in complex No. 8 is identified with the presence of two types of resonance signals at 5.37 τ and 7.27 τ due to N- CH_2 protons, a complex multiplet at 6.3 τ due to CH protons and doublet at 8.83 τ due to the CH_3 protons.

The resonance due to biphenyl protons appears in the form of a doublet, a triplet and a doublet between (2-3 τ)^{25,26}.

The i.r. and ^1H n.m.r. studies of these complexes indicate that dithiocarbamate ligands are bidentate chelating and a coordination number of 6 may be assigned to tin atom in these complexes having an octahedral geometry. Moreover, in case of octahedral geometry two structures namely *cis* and *trans* are possible. *Cis* configuration² is more consistent for these complexes as the $\nu_{(\text{C-N})}$ is towards the higher frequency (i.r. discussion).

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